

THE DEVELOPMENT OF ONLINE ENGLISH COURSES WITH THE HELP OF ISPRING SUITE

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Abstract No one disputes the fact that electronic teaching aids allow for the enrichment of the educational process by enhancing it with numerous computer technology possibilities, making it more engaging and alluring for pupils. Everyone is aware that digital textbooks are substantially different from their printed equivalents. When instructional materials are presented with multimedia elements like graphics, animation, video, sound, and simulations of the dynamics of real-world events, the student is actively engaged in the learning process, which deepens and expands the learning process.

Key words: technology, modern, English methodology, English language, language learning, iSpring Suite, online course, English language courses.

The fundamental benefit of a computer textbook is its interactivity, or more specifically, the availability of immediate student feedback when "reading" such a textbook. A computer textbook may actually "follow" the way a student studies the subject matter via a variety of parameters, giving the appearance of a "virtual teacher" through pop-up hints, spoken slander, related animation clips, and video clips.

A system for tracking knowledge acquisition and assessment is also included with a full-fledged electronic textbook, and it is likewise arranged utilizing its interactive components. In this view, e-learning tools are now quite significant in the educational process, although there are a number of issues.

The conclusion was made that certain of the electronic educational publications produced by developers in different fields and suggested for students

and schoolchildren should not be used consistently in the educational process after carefully examining them. This is because of a variety of factors, including the very large volume of some textbooks, the incompatibility of the textbook's content with the course offerings at a specific university (or the uneven distribution of information among different sections), the dearth of problem-solving examples, and financial considerations because not every university can afford to buy expensive textbooks for every student.

We have determined the primary requirements for the English online courses and workbooks by studying the experiences of eminent scientists from foreign countries and the Central Asian countries, as well as domestic literature, and exchanging experience, having studied works, analyzing articles related to electronic educational publications, and studying the concept of informatization of the education sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

1. Establishing objectives and goals.
2. Material selection and organization.
3. A definition of the textbook's structural components
4. Developing the design.
5. Implementation, approval, and revision of the textbook.

It should be emphasized that the aforementioned specifications must be met by anyone interested in developing an EMS. Teachers in a variety of subjects, including computer science instructors, are interested in the production of electronic publications. Due to their lack of expertise in the area of self-creating electronic textbooks using programming, many of them face considerable challenges while trying to create their own electronic textbooks (ETS) in the areas they teach.

Any instructor active in the development of electronic educational publications, as well as those who are unqualified in this field, may be interested in the program suggested by the authors for producing electronic textbooks.

On the basis of the available data, it is suggested to develop an EMS using systems that make use of general-purpose tools from the Microsoft Office suite, such

as the PowerPoint software, and the iSpring Suite program for converting PowerPoint presentations to flash format. The advantages of Microsoft PowerPoint include its quick creation time, lack of additional programming or database expertise requirements, and ability to incorporate objects from other software programs. A substantial fraction of the already available e-learning courses was made using the Microsoft PowerPoint application, both internationally and in the CIS nations, including Uzbekistan.

But PowerPoint's capabilities are insufficient to build a whole e-course. For uploading to a distance learning system, the e-course format in particular has to be compliant with the SCORM or AICC standards (LMS). Furthermore, classes that employ PowerPoint presentations frequently include extra components like quizzes, assignments, audio or video accompanies, etc. A broad variety of tools are available for creating electronic courses based on PowerPoint on the global market for eLearning software. Among these, Articulate Studio, Adobe Presenter, and particularly the iSpring Suite are the most popular.

iSpring collaborates with significant e-learning platforms and is a Microsoft Gold Partner. A reputable tool for developing PowerPoint eLearning courses is called iSpring Suite. You may build and publish a course using iSpring in many steps:

1. Creating a training program using a PowerPoint presentation as the foundation;
2. Production of the accompanying audio and video;
3. Creating interactive tests;
4. Development of dynamic blocks;
5. LMS publication.

Excellent resources for creating EPM include Microsoft PowerPoint and the iSpring Suite flash presentation software. Regardless of your background, you may make a fantastic EPM with the aid of these apps.

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